

Production of bio-plastic from tapioca pearls starch

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ABSTRACT

Bio-plastic are an ecofriendly alternative to conventional plastics derived from renewable resources like starch. The biodegradable plastic can be prepared with the help of different types of starch such as corn starch, potato starch and tapioca starch. Tapioca starch is used in the preparation of biodegradable plastic because of its renewable, biodegradable, non-toxic, cost effective, water solubility and film forming ability. Tapioca is extracted from the cassava plant, scientifically known as *Manihot esculenta*. Tapioca is commonly known as cassava. Tapioca pearls were taken from nearby store, and the pearls were grinded with the help of mortar and pestle to obtain a fine powder of tapioca starch. Organic colors were used in preparation of bioplastic because they are ecofriendly, non-toxic, biodegradable and cost effective. The organic color used in the preparation of bioplastic was magenta and yellow which was extracted from beetroot and turmeric. The preparation of bioplastic was carried out in lab. The tapioca pearl starch was then added in given amount in aluminium container with required amount of glycerin, vinegar and distilled water over flame. Then the sheet of bioplastic was prepared by spreading it over and drying it at room temperature respectively. Similarly, the same procedure was followed and the mixture was poured in moulds of different shapes to obtain desired shape toy. The bioplastic sheet and toy were observed and their characteristics were noted. These bioplastics were then allowed to degrade by various methods like soil degradation, water degradation and microbial degradation. In this paper Bioplastic which we prepared is useful because it is ecofriendly alternative to regular plastic and also it is biodegradable, safer for humans and animals, non-toxic, renewable, it reduces plastic pollution and has low carbon footprint.

Keywords: Bioplastic, Biodegradable, Ecofriendly, Tapioca pearl starch, Glycerin

INTRODUCTION

Starch is the major polysaccharide used in the production of bio-plastic. Most of the green plants produce polysaccharides as an energy store. Starch is a carbohydrate that contains greater amount of glucose units, combined through glycosidic linkages. Pure starch is white in color. The starch powder does not possess any specific taste or odour. While heating the starch, it becomes a paste and the viscosity is also increased.

High amylose starch is a smart reserve to use as an obstruction in packing materials. Due to the low price, renewability, and having decent mechanical properties, it was used to produce decomposable films to partly or else completely substitute the plastic polymers. The formula of starch is $(C_6H_{10}O_5)_n$, consist two types of starch molecules: Amylose and Amylopectin. (Marichelvam et al. 2019) The percentage of amylose and amylopectin content in various starches is shown below:

SOURCE	AMYLOSE (%)	AMYLOPECTIN (%)
Corn	28	72
Potato	17.8	82.2
Rice	35	65
Banana	17	83
Tapioca	16.7	83.3

Tapioca starch, also known as tapioca flour, is a fine, white powder. It is widely used in cooking, baking and various industrial applications. It has high viscosity when heated in water, forming a thick gel like paste, making it as excellent thickening agent. Tapioca starch gelatinizes at relatively low temperatures. When cooled, tapioca starch forms a clear, glossy gel which is beneficial for many purposes. It provides elasticity. It is used in making tapioca pearls commonly called a boba. Tapioca starch is use in the production of adhesives due to its strong binding properties. It consists mainly carbohydrates with very little protein or fat. It has long shelf life when stored in cool and dry place. (Marichelvam et al. 2019). Biodegradation of plastic involves specific changes in plastic material's chemical and physical properties by the action of microorganisms like fungi, bacteria, actinomycetes, etc. (Ishigaki et al. 2004).

Plastics are degraded both aerobically and anaerobically. Aerobic biodegradation involves the degradation of plastic in the availability of oxygen. The microbes use oxygen as an electron acceptor to break down plastic material into more minor organic compounds, leaning behind CO₂ and water as the by-product. Anaerobic biodegradation is the breakdown of plastic waste in the unavailability of oxygen. Microbes use nitrate, sulfate, and CO₂ as electron acceptors, breaking the organic chemicals into smaller components (Mohe et al. 2008, Priyanka and Archana et al. 2011, Haider et al. 2019). The primary mechanism behind plastic biodegradation is microorganisms sticking on the polymer surface's hydro-

philic end. After being attached to the polymer surface, the microbes use the latter as a carbon source and obtain nutrition for growth. These microorganisms reduce extracellular enzymes, which act on specific sites in the plastic material (Shah et al. 2014). These enzymes act directly on plastic, converting the polymer into a shorter chain and dimers, monomers, and oligomers. The monomer of small size enters the cell to be hydrolyzed by an internal enzyme (Shah et al. 2008, Sivan et al.2011). The final stage of biodegradation is the assimilation of monomers into a microbe to generate cellular biomass, CO₂, and methane, depending upon oxygen availability. Several factors affect the process of degradation. The type of organism, molecular weight and density of the polymer, molecular composition, hardness, physical form of polymer, pH, and moisture content. (Shikha et al. 2023). Different factors affecting the decomposition activity of bioplastic including pretreatment, microorganism and characteristics of polymer. The general characteristics of polymer include molecular weight, mobility, and nature of plasticizers, tactility and crystallinity. The decomposition activity usually take place in optimal condition including humid conditions because hydrophilic enzymes usually occur in moist environment. In soil, various organisms including bacteria, fungi or worms secrete amylase enzyme in external environment which breaks down starch. (Harma et al. 2017). This enzyme degrades the insoluble starch material to soluble products which usually absorbed by microbial cells, these products include maltose and glucose. During decomposition, the large polymers are degraded into monomers by breaking hydrogen bonds through enzymes, thus viscosity is reduced and the product is liquified. (Shah et al. 2008). Plastic has been a vital part of our life. Plastics are the most common thing used everywhere in the world for packaging, water bottles, many electronic devices etc. So, plastics have been used everywhere and it has led to many problems such as soil infertility, stop up in water bodies and the worst thing is they are not biodegradable (Bruno et al. 2011). People use plastic very often and after use the plastic it is been sent into the garbage and here comes the actual problem that is plastic is non-biodegradable which means plastic cannot be removed from the environment and this releases out lots of harmful gases. Plastic can neither be burnt or it can neither be degraded into the soil. Plastic wastes cause severe issues to environment since it does not undergo any bio degradation process (Arikan et al. 2015).

Development of biodegradable plastics is an alternative to this problem. Biodegradable plastics are known as green materials because it is friendly to environment. So, that's why researchers have been focusing on the use of the remains of food and sustainable items as biodegradable plastic items. Importance of plastic is increasing day by day (Musini et al 2020). Plastic is an important part of everyday life. Plastic is a synthetic organic polymer. In this era plastic is a very essential part of basic routine life. Basically, plastic term is used to refer those products which are produced by any synthetic or semi synthetic methods which are constantly used in our routine life. In the world, the total production of plastic is around 400 million tons per year 2022. Polythene plastic films, such as low-density polythene (LDPE) and high-density polythene (HDPE) are being used to produce a variety of polyethylene plastic films, and the drawback of this plastic is its non- degradability. Over 1000 million tons of plastic were predisposed of as unwanted elements, and they might take several hundreds of years to decay. The percentage of plastics in municipal solid waste continues to grow rapidly. When plastic wastes are dumped in landfills, they interact with water and form hazardous chemicals, and the quality of drinking water may also be affected (Shah et al 2017).

Applications of Bioplastic

1. Packaging the use of bioplastics for shopping bags is already very common. After their initial use they can be reused as bags for organic waste and then can be composted. Trays and containers for fruit, vegetables, eggs and meat, bottles for soft drinks and dairy products and blister foils for fruit and vegetables are also already widely manufactured from bioplastics.
2. Catering Products Catering products belong to the group of perishable plastics. Disposable crockery and cutlery, as well as pots and bowls, pack foils for hamburgers and straws are being dumped after a single use, together with food-leftovers, forming huge amounts of waste, particularly at big events.
3. Gardening Within the agricultural economy and the gardening sector mulch foils made of biodegradable material and flower pots made of decomposable bioplastics are predominantly used due to their adjustable lifespan and the fact that these materials do not leave residues in the soil.
4. Medical Products In comparison to packaging, catering or gardening sectors, the medical sector sets out completely different requirements with regards to products made of renewable and reabsorbing plastics.

Sanitary Products Due to their specific characteristics, bioplastics are used as a basic for the production of sanitary products. These materials are breathable and allow water vapor to permeate, but at the same time they are waterproof. Foils made of soft bioplastics are already used as diaper foil, bed underlay, for incontinence product ladies' sanitary products and as disposable gloves (Shah Charmi et al 2017).

Materials Used in Preparation of Bioplastic:

1. Glycerol, vinegar, and distilled water are vital in improving the properties of the final product in the manufacture of tapioca starch based biodegradable plastic films.
2. As one of the constituent biopolymers in the composition of biodegradable plastics, tapioca starch has biopolymer properties. It provides the structure and mechanical strength required for the plastic films. Starch serves as a matrix in which the other components are a constituent of the film. Therefore, it also adds strength and flexibility to the plastic film. Use of starch in biodegradable plastics is beneficial because it is renewable resource and increases the eco-friendliness of the final product. It is comparatively easier for the plastic to break down naturally in the environment than conventional plastics due to the presence of starch-based compounds, helping alleviate pollution caused by plastics.
3. In bioplastic recipes, vinegar's acidic nature makes it a good candidate for additives for starch vinegar bioplastic. Vinegar is useful in bringing the needed pH to the composition, so that the components, starch included, interact and get gelatinized. Furthermore, other vinegar properties may lead to an increase in the biodegradability of the films by assisting the breakdown of the starch.
4. Glycerol serves as a bioplastic plasticizer. It increases the flexibility and the workability of the films. With glycerol, the films are less brittle and softer, which is required in real world applications. The study pointed out that in a certain concentration of glycerol in the solution, it remarkably proved beneficial towards the quality of the bioplastic films produced from cassava starch.
5. The mixture of tapioca starch and glycerol, in conjunction with vinegar, enhances the moisture

adsorption, solubility, and biodegradability of the resulting plastic films. Biodegradable plastics are prepared using distilled water as it's the cleanest form of water. It has no impurities or contaminants. Such purity is essential for the chemical processes occurring, plastic is not blocked by undesired materials. With no impurity, we can ensure uniformity and superior quality of the end product, which is important in the making of the biodegradable plastic film.

In present paper show to reduce the use of synthetic plastics and to promote bioplastics. Bioplastic which we prepared is useful because it is ecofriendly alternative to regular plastic and also it is biodegradable, safer for humans and animals, non-toxic, renewable, it reduce plastic pollution and has low carbon footprint.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Collection of samples:

The raw materials for preparation of biodegradable plastics include tapioca pearl starch, glycerine, white vinegar, distilled water, beetroot and turmeric. Tapioca starch, beetroot, turmeric and white vinegar were purchased from nearby store. Glycerine and

distilled water were taken from Deogiri college laboratory.

Extraction of sample

A. Extraction of Starch from Tapioca Pearl:

500g of tapioca pearls were taken and soaked in distilled water for 4-5 hours. The pearls were then drained to remove excess starch present in them. The soaked water was allowed to settle for couple of hours which will lead to settling of starch at the bottom. At the same time the pearls were spreaded on filter paper and kept in hot air oven for 24-48 hrs. The starch settled at the bottom of beaker was poured on glass petri plates and were kept in hot air oven for 24 hrs. The dried pearls and starch in petri plates were then grinded in mortar and pestle to produce fine powder.

Extraction of organic colour:

Two organic color were obtained from beetroot, turmeric respectively. The beetroot was cut into small pieces and was grinded in mortar and pestle by adding little distilled water. The mixture was then filtered and the filtrate was used as organic color during the preparation of biodegradable plastic. Similarly, yellow color was obtained by grinding turmeric in mortar and pestle. The obtained powder was then used as organic color during preparation of biodegradable plastic.

Figure 1: (A) Preparation of tapioca starch ; (B) Tapioca Starch (C)Drying of tapioca starch

Figure 2: Beetroot mixture, Turmeric powder

A

B

Figure 3: Biodegradable plastic A: Bioplastic with glycerine content, B: Bioplastic with water content

Production of biodegradable plastic:

Begin by adding 1.5 g of tapioca starch, 1 ml of white vinegar, and 7 ml of distilled water into a beaker. Mix it separately with different amounts of glycerin, specifically, 0.25 g, 0.5 g, 0.75 g, and 1 g. continue stirring the mixture until it turns milky white and has a watery consistency. At the same time, use 1.5 g of corn starch, 1 ml of white vinegar, and 0.5 g of glycerin to follow the same procedure, but change the amount of water to 6 ml, 7 ml, 8 ml, and 9 ml with the goal of increasing the total water content.

Effect of The Amount of Glycerine on the Characteristic of Biodegradable Plastic: The plastic sample were prepared by varying the amount of glycerine (i.e., 0.25g, 0.5g, 0.75g, 1g) using the same production of bioplastic procedure (as per table 3).

Effect of The Amount of Glycerine on the Characteristic of Biodegradable Plastic: The plastic sample were prepared by varying water content (i.e., 6ml, 7ml, 8ml, 9ml, 10ml) using the same production of bioplastic procedure (et.al 2019) (as per table 4)

PREPARATION OF DIFFERENT SHAPES OF BIOPLASTIC

As plastic with glycerol content 0.5 was more soft, thin and translucent as compared to others. So, this plastic with glycerol composition 0.5 was taken to prepare plastic toy. In a beaker add 1.5g tapioca starch, 1ml white vinegar, 7ml distilled water, 0.5g glycerine and 2 spoons of organic color respectively. Now stir the mixture continuously until the mixture become milky white and quite watery. The beaker was put on burner and heat was set. While heating, the mixture was stirred continuously till it become more translucent and began to thicken. The clear and thicken mixture was removed from the burner and maintained the temperature at 85c for 3 minutes. Then the heated mixture was spread on moulds to obtain desired shape.

The sample was dried undisturbed at room temperature for 3 days. The sample was then removed from moulds and desired shape of bioplastic was obtained.

Degradation of bioplastic

Biodegradable behavior of bio-plastic was determined using the following test:

Figure 4: Preparation of bioplastic in different shapes

Figure 5: Preparation of bioplastic in different shapes

Soil burial degradation test

Bio-plastic were placed in soil for degradation and the following procedures were done. The 'The damage,' as described in the excerpt indicates the mass loss for all specimens placed in soil and is basically observable. Bio-plastic were cut into 5cm x 5cm. Then specimens were entrenched at a depth of 8cm for varied durations (1, 2, 3, or 4 weeks). The mass prior to degradation was the set baseline for all specimens. Post degradation, the weight of the maximum achievable bio-plastic value was taken. This process continues till complete bio-plastic degradation is attained, the biodegradability index gets computed.

Figure 6: Initial observation of degradation of bio-plastic

A

B

Figure 7: Bio-plastic degradation in week 1 & week 2

- A. G1- 10% of G1 bio-plastic was degraded, G2- 15% of G2 bio-plastic was degraded. G3- 15% of G3 bio-plastic was degraded, G4- 20% of G4 bio-plastic was degraded. W1- 20% of W1 bio-plastic was degraded, W2- 20% of W2 bio-plastic was degraded. W3- 10% of W3 bio-plastic was degraded, W4- 10% of W4 bio-plastic was degraded.
- B. G1- 40% of G1 bio-plastic was degraded, G2- 40% of G2 bio-plastic was degraded. G3- 50% of G3 bio-plastic was degraded, G4- 30% of G4 bio-plastic was degraded. W1- 20% of W1 bio-plastic was degraded, W2- 20% of W2 bio-plastic was degraded. W3- 30% of W3 bio-plastic was degraded, W4- 40% of W4 bio-plastic was degraded.

Figure 8 : Bio-plastic degradation in 3 week & 4 week

A: G1- 50% of G1 bio-plastic was degraded, G2- 60% of G2 bio-plastic was degraded. G3- 60% of G3 bio-plastic was degraded, G4- 50% of G4 bio-plastic was degraded. W1- 30% of W1 bio-plastic was degraded, W2- 30% of W2 bio-plastic was degraded. W3- 40% of W3 bio-plastic was degraded, W4- 50% of W4 bio-plastic was degraded.

B: G1- 70% of G1 bio-plastic was degraded, G2- 70% of G2 bio-plastic was degraded. G3- 70% of G3 bio-plastic was degraded, G4- 80% of G4 bio-plastic was degraded. W1- 70% of W1 bio-plastic was degraded, W2- 70% of W2 bio-plastic was degraded. W3- 80% of W3 bio-plastic was degraded, W4- 100% of W4 bio-plastic was degraded.

Figure 9: Bio-plastic degradation in week 5 : G1- 100% of G1 bio-plastic was degraded, G2- 90% of G2 bio-plastic was degraded. G3- 90% of G3 bio-plastic was degraded, G4- 90% of G4 bio-plastic was degraded. W1- 90% of W1 bio-plastic was degraded, W2- 80% of W2 bio-plastic was degraded. W3- 80% of W3 bio-plastic was degraded, W4- 100% of W4 bio-plastic was degraded

WATER DEGRADATION TEST:

The plastic sample weight was measured respectively, then the sample was soaked in water for three weeks at room temperature.

MICROBIAL DEGRADATION TEST:

The pieces of plastic were washed with ethanol and rinsed with distilled water in order to remove contaminants. 63 grams of nutrient broth were added to 80 ml of water to prepare the broth and further 5 ml of the nutrient broth was added to each test tube. *Bacillus subtilis* and *Pseudomonas* were separately inoculated into test tubes with nutrient broths. The bio-plastics were then placed in the test tubes alongside the respective microbes and the test tubes then placed into incubators for biodegradation purposes.

Table 1: Effect of *Pseudomonas* on bioplastic: Degradation of Bio-Plastic Containing *Pseudomonas*

Sr. No	Bioplastic Sample	Initial Observation	Final observation
1.	G1	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
2.	G2	2 x 2cm	1 x 1cm
3.	G3	2 x 2cm	0.5 x 0.5cm
4.	G4	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
5.	W1	2 x 2cm	0.7 x 0.7cm
6.	W2	2 x 2cm	1.5 x 1.5cm
7.	W3	2 x 2cm	0.2 x 0.2cm
8.	W4	2 x 2cm	0.5 x 0.5cm

Table 2: Effect of *Bacillus subtilis* on bioplastic: Degradation of Bio-Plastic Containing *Bacillus Subtilis*

Sr. No	Bioplastic Sample	Initial Observation	Final observation
1.	G1	2x 2cm	Totally degraded
2.	G2	2x 2cm	Totally degraded
3.	G3	2x 2cm	Totally degraded
4.	G4	2x 2cm	Totally degraded
5.	W1	2x 2cm	0.2x0.2cm
6.	W2	2x 2cm	1.2x1.2cm
7.	W3	2x 2cm	0.2x0.2cm
8.	W4	2x 2cm	0.5x0.5cm

RESULTS

In this study, biodegradable plastic was produced from tapioca starch by changing the proportions of to glycerine (0.25g, 0.5g, 0.75g, 1g) and water (6ml, 7ml, 8ml, 9ml). It was observed that the viscosity of the plastic prepared is directly proportional to the extent of glycerine used. The more the amount of glycerin, the greater the viscosity of the plastic. The drying time depends on the amount of glycerin used. The amount of drying time is greater when higher amounts of glycerin are utilized. Furthermore, the glycerin content controlled the thickness of the plastic. It was found that higher amounts of glycerin resulted in thicker layers while lower amounts led to thinner layers. More water would result in more bubbles being formed in the plasticky structure and increased

translucence. Of all the samples prepared, the optimum product was made using tapioca starch by 1.5g, vinegar 1ml, glycerin 0.5 and distilled water 7m as this required lower drying times, contained no bubbles and possessed better tensile strength. The prepared plastic was dried for three days in room temperature and moderate humidity.

Effect of Glycerine Content on Preparation of Biodegradable Plastic

The effect of glycerine on bioplastic shown as, 0.25 g of glycerine produces soft, thin and more transparent plastic; 0.5g of glycerine gives good tensile strength with little viscosity; 0.75g of glycerine results in good tensile strength but is more viscous and thicker; 1 g of glycerine leads to low tensile strength, high viscosity, more bubbles and thick texture.

Table 3: Effect of glycerine on bioplastic

Sr. No	Tapioca Starch	Water	Vinegar	Amount of Glycerine (G)	Remarks
1.	1.5g	7ml	1ml	0.25	Soft, thin and translucent
2.	1.5g	7ml	1ml	0.5	Good tensile strength, little viscous, no bubbles, thin and translucent.
3.	1.5g	7ml	1ml	0.75	Good tensile strength, more viscous, thick, fairly little bubbles and translucent.
4.	1.5g	7ml	1ml	1	Low tensile strength, most viscous, more bubbles, translucent and thicker.

Table 4: Effect of water on bioplastic:

Sr. No	Tapioca Starch	Glycerine	Vinegar	Volume of Water (ML)	Remarks
1.	1.5g	0.5g	1ml	6	More viscous, thick and translucent.
2.	1.5g	0.5g	1ml	7	Viscous, no bubbles and translucent.
3.	1.5g	0.5g	1ml	8	Less viscous, contains fair amount of air bubbles and translucent.
4.	1.5g	0.5g	1ml	9	Soft, contains more amount of air bubbles and translucent.

The effect of glycerine on bioplastic shown as, 6ml water leads to more viscous, thick and translucent bioplastic; 7 ml water leads to more viscous and translucent bioplastic; 8 ml of water leads to less viscous and translucent bioplastic; 9ml of water gives soft and translucent bioplastic.

MICROBIAL DEGRADATION TEST:

Table 5: Degradation of Bio-Plastic Containing *Pseudomonas*:

Sr. No	Bioplastic Sample	Initial Observation	Final Observation
1.	G1	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
2.	G2	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
3.	G3	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
4.	G4	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
5.	W1	2 x 2cm	0.2x0.2cm
6.	W2	2 x 2cm	1.2x1.2cm
7.	W3	2 x 2cm	0.2x0.2cm
8.	W4	2 x 2cm	0.5x0.5cm

Degradation of bioplastic shows that G1 and G2 are completely degraded; G3 and G4 shows partial degradation; W1, W2, W3 and W4 shows least degradation.

Table 6: Degradation of Bio-Plastic Containing *Bacillus Subtilis*:

Sr. No	Bioplastic Sample	Initial Observation	Final Observation
1.	G1	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
2.	G2	2 x 2cm	1 x 1cm
3.	G3	2 x 2cm	0.5 x 0.5cm
4.	G4	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
5.	W1	2 x 2cm	0.7x0.7cm
6.	W2	2 x 2cm	1.5x1.5cm
7.	W3	2 x 2cm	0.2x0.2cm
8.	W4	2 x 2cm	0.5x0.5cm

Degradation of bioplastic shows that G1, G2, G3 and G4 are completely degraded; W1, W2, W3 and W4 shows least degradation.

WATER DEGRADATION TEST:

Table 7: Degradation of bio-plastic in water:

Sr. No	Bioplastic Sample	Initial Observation	Final Observation
1.	G1	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
2.	G2	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
3.	G3	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
4.	G4	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
5.	W1	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
6.	W2	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
7.	W3	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
8.	W4	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded

Degradation of bioplastic shows that G1, G2, G3 and G4 are completely degraded; W1, W2, W3 and W4 shows complete degradation.

SOIL DEGRADATION TEST:

Table 8: Degradation of bio-plastic in soil:

Sr. No	Bioplastic Sample	Initial Observation	Final observation
1.	G1	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
2.	G2	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
3.	G3	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
4.	G4	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
5.	W1	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
6.	W2	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
7.	W3	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded
8.	W4	2 x 2cm	Totally degraded

Degradation of bioplastic shows that G1, G2, G3 and G4 are completely degraded; W1, W2, W3 and W4 shows complete degradation

DISCUSSION:

Plastic waste has become significant environmental problem with millions of tons of plastic waste which is harmful to both environment as well as animals and humans. Biodegradable plastic has a promising solution to this problem. As biodegradable plastic can be easily degraded in soil, water and by microorganism which causes less pollution as compared to regular plastic. Compared to regular plastic bioplastic is less harmful as it takes about 3-4 months to degrade. Also, it causes less water, soil and air pollution.

CONCLUSION

The emerging technologies in the field of packaging include biodegradable plastics, regarded as one of the greatest innovations in recent times. The race to commercialize the patent for this technology is simply unmatched. The extent of the adoption of biodegradable plastics will depend on society's belief in conservation and their eagerness to protect the environment. In and of itself, there exists a plethora of materials and substances to discover and devise more applications for creating biodegradable plastics. In this experiment, varying amounts of ingredients like water (6ml, 7ml, 8ml, 9ml) and glycerine (0.25g, 0.5g, 0.75g, 1g) were used to create biodegradable plastic. The best conditions for creating biodegradable plastic include 1.5g of tapioca pearl starch, 1ml of vinegar, 0.5g of glycerin, and 7ml of distilled water. Every year, huge volumes of plastic are thrown away. It can be assumed that the use of plastic bags will rise; hence the production of plastic waste will proportionally grow. It is crucial to find a reliable solution to manage such waste. The same plastic bags will be tested further in composting both in laboratory setting and natural environment.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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